

Kinetic determination of cysteine in trace amounts based on its inhibitory effect

Amarika Singh* and Anupma Singh

Institute of Engineering and Technology, Sitapur Road, Lucknow-226 021, Uttar Pradesh, India

E-mail : amarikasinh@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received online 23 January 2013, revised 20 March 2013, accepted 12 May 2013

Abstract : Cysteine is a sulphur containing α -amino acid having chemical formula $\text{HO}_2\text{CCH}(\text{NH}_2)\text{CH}_2\text{SH}$. Its sulphur atom has been shown to inhibit the mercury catalysed substitution of cyanide in hexacyanoferrate(II) by phenanthroline [Phen]. The inhibitory effect is due to the binding capacity of catalyst with the inhibitor. The reaction was followed spectrophotometrically in aqueous medium at 528 nm by the formation of a dark coloured complex, $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{Phen}]^{3-}$ at $\text{pH} = 3.0 \pm 0.02$, $\text{temp.} = 25.0 \pm 0.1$ °C, ionic strength (μ) = 0.05 M (KNO_3). Linear calibration curves were obtained at different times (A_t) and different cysteine concentrations, under the above conditions. The detection limit was 5×10^{-7} M, the Michaelis-Menten constant (K_m) and equilibrium constant for the complex of catalyst and inhibitor (K_{CI}) and for the complex of catalyst and substrate (K_s) were calculated from the kinetic data. A general mechanistic scheme is also proposed for this reaction.

Keywords : Cysteine, inhibition effect, kinetic, phenanthroline, hexacyanoferrate(II).

Introduction

Reactivity of cysteine and its derivatives has been studied in polypeptides¹ and proteins². Cysteine has a strong tendency to bind with heavy metals like Hg, Pb, Cd^{3,4} and used to reduce toxic effects of alcohol⁵. Its ligand substitution reaction with Au^{III} complexes⁶ and Pt^{II} complexes⁷⁻¹⁰ have been studied extensively.

Numerous kinetic studies of metal catalysed *N*-heterocyclic ligand substitution reaction of hexacyanoferrate(II) have been studied¹¹⁻¹³. Trace determination of many inorganic ions have also been investigated¹⁴⁻²⁵. Addition of a complexing agent to a metal catalysed reaction may result in either promotion or inhibition of the reaction¹⁴. Linear relation of the added ligand can often be obtained by simple empirical treatment of rate data. This forms the basis of determination of small amounts of complexing agents by the method known as "Kinetic Method" developed by us here.

We have already studied the kinetic determination of Hg^{II} at trace levels using its catalytic effect on ligand substitution reaction between hexacyanoferrate(II) and phenanthroline. The reaction was followed spectrophotometrically at 528 nm (λ_{max} of a dark coloured complex $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_5\text{Phen}]^{3-}$). It is used in treatment of leukemia⁶

and as antidote for negative effect of alcohol including liver damage⁵. The above cited indicator reaction can also be used for determination of sulphur containing ligands. These ligands have high formation metal constants than those of the ligands containing N and O atoms even at low pH values and are thus best suited for the study. Cysteine forms chelates with Hg^{II} and inhibit the rate of the indicator reaction. The optimum conditions for the indicator reaction like concentration of reagents, temperature, pH and ionic strength have been studied here. There is limited information available in literature to determine these complexing agents^{33,34} by metal catalysed reactions²⁵⁻³². Moreover, the analysis requires expensive instruments of voltammetry and others^{35,36}.

Therefore, the need for a simple and less expensive technique is always welcomed. The present paper describes the determination of cysteine in trace levels based on its inhibitory effect of the mercury catalysed ligand substitution reaction between hexacyanoferrate(II) and phenanthroline.

Experimental

Materials :

Double distilled water was used throughout to prepare all solutions. All the chemicals used in this study were of

analytical reagent grade. The solution of $K_4[Fe(CN)_6] \cdot 3H_2O$ (Merck, Germany) was prepared by weighing a desired amount and kept in dark in coloured bottles. The fresh solutions of phenanthroline (S.D. Fine Chemicals) was prepared in double distilled water everyday before starting the kinetic run. A stock solution of $HgCl_2$ (BDH) was prepared by weighing and dissolving $HgCl_2$ in water. Dilute solutions of $HgCl_2$ were also prepared daily in order to prevent loss due to its adsorption on glass surfaces. KNO_3 (A.R. Glaxo) was used to maintain ionic strength in reaction medium. Cysteine hydrochloride is readily oxidized by atmospheric oxygen at room temperature³⁷ so, a stock solution of this reagent was stored at low temperature and was standardized every time against ferricyanide before use³⁸. The pH of the reaction mixture was maintained at a desired value using potassium phthalate (A.R. Qualigens Fine Chemicals) sodium hydroxide buffer³⁹.

Apparatus :

All the reactant solutions were equilibrated at 25 °C by keeping them inside environmental chamber in order to maintain the desired temperature within the accuracy of ± 0.1 °C. Genesis model No. 10 UV was used to record the spectra of the reaction. The pH measurements were made on a digital pH meter of Sio-global pH meter.

Procedure :

1 mL of Hg^{2+} solution of a fixed concentration was taken and 1 mL of inhibitor or complexing agent of various concentrations was mixed and kept for 10 min to ensure formation of CI. Then 3 mL of buffer followed by 1 mL of phenanthroline of specific concentration was added. The reaction was started by adding 1 mL of ferrocyanide solution. The reaction mixture was shaken vigorously and then transferred to a cuvette of 1 cm path length kept in a cell compartment maintained at 25.0 ± 0.1 °C. A fixed time procedure at 528 nm was used for measuring the initial rate to establish the calibration curves.

The chosen reaction conditions are : $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-} = 3.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, $[Phen] = 1.5 \times 10^{-5} M$, $[Hg^{2+}] = 7.5 \times 10^{-3}$, $pH = 3.0 \pm 0.02$, $temp. = 25.0 \pm 0.1$ °C, ionic strength (μ) = 0.05 M (KNO_3).

Results and discussion

The phenanthroline substitution of the co-ordinated cyanide in hexacyanoferrate(II) is homogeneously catalysed

by (Hg^{2+}) ions in acidic medium at normal temperature. A detailed kinetic and mechanistic study of this reaction has already been studied. Traces of (Hg^{2+}) ions enhance the rate of the reaction to a very good extent and the reaction rate was followed spectrophotometrically at 528 nm, due to the formation of product $[Fe(CN)_5Phen]^{3-}$. The studies show that there is no interference from the reactants $[Hg^{2+}]$, $K_4[Fe(CN)_6]$ and $[Phen]$. The concentration of cysteine was varied from mole ratio 0.5 to 0.6. The absorbance changes observed for cysteine system after a fixed time interval are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Determination of cysteine by its inhibitory effect on Hg^{2+} catalysed substitution of cyanide in $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-}$ by Phen, $[Fe(CN)_6]^{4-} = 1.5 \times 10^{-2} M$, $[Phen] = 3.0 \times 10^{-4} M$, $[Hg^{2+}] = 1.5 \times 10^{-7} M$, $pH = 3.0 \pm 0.02$, $temp. = 25 \pm 0.1$ °C, $I = 0.05 M$

Cysteine taken $\times 10^6 (M)$	A_t Absorbance after t min	
	A_{15}	A_{20}
2.50	0.155	0.173
2.32	0.162	0.181
1.81	0.173	0.196
1.66	0.191	0.225
1.36	0.203	0.287
1.0	0.298	0.326

Effect of pH on the reaction rate :

The pH dependence of the reaction rate was studied in the pH range 1–8 at 3 time points at A_t (where $t = 10, 15, 20$ min). The change in absorbance at 528 nm as a function of pH is shown in Fig. 1. The rate of the reaction is slow at lower pH, attains a maximum value at $pH = 3.0 \pm 0.02$, then falls off again. This decrease is attributed to the deficiency of protons needed to regenerate the catalytic species or due to decrease in $[Hg^{2+}]$ as a result of hydrolytic precipitation. Thus, pH value of 3.0 ± 0.02 becomes critical for this system and should be maintained at optimum using phthalate-sodium hydroxide buffer³⁹.

Effects of reagent concentration, temperature and ionic strength :

The effect of phenanthroline concentration was studied at the optimum pH and $[Phen]$ range of 2.0×10^{-4} to $2.5 \times 10^{-3} M$. On the basis of studies done, it was revealed that the rate of reaction increases linearly up to the concentration $1.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ and then finally levels off at $[Phen] \geq 1.5 \times 10^{-3} M$. Thus, the $[Phen]$ of $1.5 \times 10^{-3} M$ was selected as optimal.

Fig. 1. Effect of pH on the Hg^{II} -catalysed substitution of CN^- in hexacyanoferrate(II) by [Phen]. Conditions : $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-} = 1.50 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Phen}] = 1.50 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Hg}^{2+}] = 1.5 \times 10^{-5} \text{ M}$, $\mu = 0.03 \text{ M}$ (KNO_3) and temp. = $25.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

The effect of $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ on the initial rate was studied in the range 2.5×10^{-4} to $1.5 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$, keeping all other values constant. The plot of log initial rate vs log $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ shows a variable order dependence on $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ changing from first order at lower concentrations to a fractional order at higher concentrations but certainly not tending towards zero. A $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ of $3.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$ was chosen optimal.

The influence of temperature on the rate of the catalysed and uncatalysed reaction was studied in the range of 20–50 $^\circ\text{C}$. The reaction obeyed Eyring equation and optimum rate was achieved at 25 $^\circ\text{C}$ which was selected for further studies. The effect of ionic strength (μ) on the rate of catalysed reaction in the range 0.02 to 0.05 M showed increase and then decrease in the reaction rate. An ionic strength of 0.05 M gives measurable change in absorbance values, which was selected for further studies.

For analytical applications, the catalytic effect of $[\text{Hg}^{2+}]$ on the rate of catalysed reaction was studied in the range 1.5×10^{-7} to $9.0 \times 10^{-7} \text{ M}$ under the conditions, $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-} = 5.5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Phen}] = 2.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $\text{pH} = 3.0 \pm 0.02$, temp. = $25 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $\mu = 0.05 \text{ M}$ (KNO_3). The plot of absorbance after 10 min (A_{10}) vs $[\text{Hg}^{2+}]$ was found to be linear in the $[\text{Hg}^{2+}]$ range of 4.5

$\times 10^{-7}$ to $9.5 \times 10^{-6} \text{ M}$. A $[\text{Hg}^{2+}]$ of $6.5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ M}$ provides sufficient absorbance change, and hence was used for determination of cysteine.

Kinetic role of inhibiting ligands :

Based on the consideration that inhibitor cysteine is competitive with the catalyst⁴⁰ and is reversible for the mercury catalysed reaction between phenanthroline and hexacyanoferrate(II) thereby, depleting the concentration of catalyst and reducing the rate of the reaction. The reaction scheme proposed earlier⁴¹ and modified to include the rate of inhibitor denoted by I, is outlined below :

If we take $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-}$ present in non-rate limiting excess condition as S and its initial concentration by $[S_0]$, it is simple to derive the rate expression by comparing it with enzyme catalysed reaction of a single substrate in presence of an inhibitor. The reaction rate in presence of catalyst can be given by eq. (1),

$$V_0 = \frac{V_{\max}}{1 + \frac{K_m}{[S_0]}} \quad (1)$$

This equation can be transformed to Line Weaver-Burk⁴² form as eq. (2),

$$\frac{1}{V_0} = \frac{1}{V_{\max}} + \frac{K_m}{V_{\max}} \cdot \frac{1}{[S_0]} \quad (2)$$

Here, V_0 is the reaction rate in presence of catalyst only, V_{\max} is the maximum attainable rate at a particular catalyst concentration in presence of a non-rate limiting quantity of substrate and K_m is the Michaelis-Menten constant, which is roughly equivalent to the dissociation constant of the catalyst substrate complex.

In presence of inhibitor, the rate of the reaction can be represented as eq. (3),

$$V_i = \frac{V_{\max}}{1 + \frac{K'_m}{[S_0]}} \quad (3)$$

where K'_m is the new apparent Michaelis-Menten constant in presence of the inhibitor. It can be shown that

$$K'_m = K_m \left[1 + \frac{[I_0]}{K'_{CI}} \right] \quad (4)$$

Substituting this value in eq. (3) we get,

$$V_i = \frac{V_{\max}}{\frac{K_m}{[S_0]} \left[1 + \frac{[I_0]}{K'_{CI}} \right]} \quad (5)$$

Here, V_i is the reaction rate in presence of inhibitor (at a fixed catalyst concentration), and K'_{CI} is the dissociation constant of the catalyst inhibitor (C-I) complex.

Eq. (5) can also be transformed to eq. (6) in Line Weaver-Burk form as

$$\frac{1}{V_i} - \frac{1}{V_{\max}} = \frac{K_m}{V_{\max}[S_0]} + \frac{K_m}{V_{\max}[S_0]} \cdot \frac{[I_0]}{K'_{CI}} \quad (6)$$

In the above equation, V_{\max} is not an experimental quantity, but it is obtained from the intercept of the plot of $1/V_0$ vs $1/[S_0]$ from eq. (2) in absence of inhibitor as shown in Fig. 2. The slope of this plot gives the value of K_m as 72.71.

Fig. 2. Linear plot of $1/V_0$ vs $1/[S_0]$. Conditions : $[\text{Hg}^{2+}] = 1.5 \times 10^{-6} M$, $[\text{Phen}] = 2.5 \times 10^{-2} M$, $\text{pH} = 3.0 \pm 0.02$, $\text{temp.} = 25 \pm 0.1^\circ \text{C}$, $\mu = 0.03 M (\text{KNO}_3)$.

Eq. (6) also works when the inhibitor 'I' forms a C-I type chelate with the catalyst 'C' and for this reaction no substrate inhibitor is seen. Under these conditions a plot of $\left[\frac{1}{V_i} - \frac{1}{V_{\max}} \right]$ vs $[I_0]$ gives a straight line as shown in Fig. 3. The intercept of this plot give a K_m that agrees with the value calculated here by plotting $\frac{1}{V_0}$ vs $\frac{1}{[S_0]}$ the slope of which gives a K'_{CI} that corresponds to the cysteine complex of mercury, as listed in Table 2.

The reciprocal of this K_m is approximately equal to the stability constant K_s ($\log K_s = 1.91 \pm 0.98$) of the catalyst substrate complex. The values of the stability constant (K_{CI}) of the CI complexes and its reciprocal K'_{CI} are also given in Table 2. The competitive, non-competi-

Fig. 3. Determination of K'_{Cl} and K_m in presence of inhibitor cysteine. Conditions : $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-} = 3.0 \times 10^{-2} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Phen}] = 1.5 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Hg}^{2+}] = 7.5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ M}$, $\text{pH} = 3.0 \pm 0.02$, $\mu = 0.05 \text{ M}$ (KNO_3) and $\text{temp.} = 25 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

Table 2. Conditional formation constants under optimal conditions

A	Mercury - Inhibitor complex	$\log K_{Cl}$
	Inhibitor - Cysteine	5.92 ± 0.02
B	Michaelis-Menten constant	$\log K_m$
	Inhibitor - Cysteine	1.86 ± 0.02
C	Catalyst - Substrate complex	$\log K_S$
		1.91 ± 0.03

tive and incompetent behavior of inhibiting ligands can also be differentiated, although this is beyond the scope of this study.

Analytical applications :

The validity of the proposed method was tested by the recovery experiments performed on synthetic mixtures (SMs) of water sulphide ions as shown in Table 3. The

Table 3. Determination of 0.3 and 0.6 mM of cysteine in synthetic mixtures under conditions : $[\text{Fe}(\text{CN})_6]^{4-} = 3.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Phen}] = 2.0 \times 10^{-3} \text{ M}$, $[\text{Hg}^{2+}] = 7.5 \times 10^{-7} \text{ M}$, $\text{pH} = 3.0 \pm 0.02$, $\text{temp.} = 25.0 \pm 0.1 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, Ionic strength = 0.05 M (KNO_3)

Synthetic mixtures (SM)	Composition of SM (μM)	Found (μM) proposed method	Recovery (%)
SM1	Cys (0.3) + S^{2-} (0.3)	0.30	100.0
SM2	Cys (0.3) + S^{2-} (1.0)	0.32	102.2
SM3	Cys (0.6) + S^{2-} (1.0)	0.61	101.7
SM4	Cys (0.9) + S^{2-} (1.0)	0.92	102.2

synthetic mixture analysis results in a reasonably good recovery. Under the specified conditions, the detection limit for cysteine was $5.4 \times 10^{-7} \text{ M}$.

References

1. B. Cerzegorz, K. Tanja and G. P. David, *Biochemistry*, 1998, **37**, 8965.
2. S. S. Carolyn and K. A. Chris, *Nature Rev. Mol. Cell. Biol.*, 2002, **3**, 836.
3. L. J. Stephen and B. M. Jeremy, "Principles of Bioinorganic Chemistry", University Science Books, Mill Valley, CA, 1994.
4. B. H. David and C. M. L. Gail, *J. Nutr.*, 1987, **117**, 1003.
5. S. Herbert, P. M. Clarence, S. G. George and G. J. Leon, *Inflam. Res.*, 1974, **4**, 125.
6. M. Milovanovic, A. Djekovic, V. Volarevic, B. Petrovic, N. Arsenijevic and Z. D. Bugarcic, *J. Inorg. Biochem.*, 2010, **104**, 944.
7. M. K. Howe-Grant, K. C. Wu, W. R. Bauer and S. J. Loppard, *Biochemistry*, 1976, **151**, 4339.
8. E. M. A. Ratilla, H. M. Brothers and N. M. Kostic, *Journal of the American Society*, 1987, **109**, 4592.
9. S. D. Cummings, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 2009, **253**, 449.
10. T. Soldatovic, Z. D. Bugarcic and R. Van Eldik, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2009, **23**, 4526.
11. R. M. Naik, R. K. Tewari, P. K. Singh and S. B. S. Yadav, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 2007, **39**, 447.
12. R. M. Naik, J. Sarkar and D. D. Chaturvedi, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 2005, **37**, 222.
13. S. Prasad, *Trans. Met. Chem.*, 2003, **28**, 1.
14. H. A. Mottola, "Kinetic Aspects of Analytical Chemistry", John Wiley, New York, 1988.
15. H. A. Mottola and Perez-Bendito, *Anal. Chem.*, 1996, **68**, 257R.
16. S. Prasad, *Anal. Chim. Acta*, 2005, **540**, 173.
17. S. Prasad, *J. Anal. Chem.*, 2005, **60**, 587.
18. S. Prasad, *Anal. Lett.*, 2004, **37**, 2851.
19. S. Prasad and T. Halafihi, *Mikrochim. Acta*, 2003, **142**, 237.
20. T. Kawashima, S. Nakano, M. Tabata and Tanaka, *Trends Anal. Chem.*, 1997, **16**, 132.
21. Y. L. Feng, H. Narasaki, L. C. Tian, S. M. Wu and H. Y. Chen, *Anal. Sci.*, 1999, **15**, 915.
22. R. M. Naik, P. K. Singh, R. Rastogi, R. Singh and A. Agarwal, *Annali di Chimica*, 2007, **97**, 1169.
23. R. M. Naik, A. Srivastava and S. Prasad, *Spectrochimica Acta, Part A*, 2008, **69**, 193.
24. S. Prasad, R. M. Naik and A. Srivastava, *Spectrochimica Acta, Part A*, 2008, **70**, 958.
25. R. M. Naik and J. Sarkar, *Ind. J. Chem. Tech.*, 2005,

- 12, 563.
26. A. Giannousios and C. Papadopoulos, *Analyst*, 1996, **121**, 413.
27. M. H. Cordoba, P. Vinas and C. S. Pedreno, *Talanta*, 1985, **22**, 221.
28. A. M. Eleni and A. K. Michael, *Analyst*, 1987, **112**, 757.
29. M. Marquez, M. Silva and D. Perez-Bendito, *Analyst*, 1988, **113**, 1373.
30. D. P. Nikolesis and T. P. Hadjiioannon, *Anal. Chem.*, 1978, **50**, 205.
31. M. Phull and P. C. Nigam, *Talanta*, 1983, **30**, 401.
32. M. S. Gareia, C. S. Pedreno and M. I. Albero, *Analyst*, 1990, **115**, 989.
33. M. L. Luner, S. Rubio, D. P. Bendito, M. L. Carreto and C. W. Mc Leod, *Analytica Chimica Acta*, 1997, **337**, 341.
34. S. Prasad, *Microchemical Journal*, 2007, **85**, 214.
35. S. Tanaka and H. Yoshida, *Journal of Electroanalytical Chemistry and Interfacial Electrochemistry*, 1982, **137**, 261.
36. S. Tanaka and H. Yoshida, *Journal of Electroanalytical Chemistry and Inter Facial Electrochemistry*, 1983, **149**, 213.
37. P. I. Morando, E. B. Borghi, L. M. Deschtungart and M. A. Blesa, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1981, 435.
38. H. L. Mason, *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1930, **86**, 623.
39. R. C. Weast, "CRC Handbook of Chemistry and Physics", 49th ed., The Chemical Rubber Co., Ohio, 1969, Sect. D-79.
40. J. Masłowska and Leszezynska, *Talanta*, 1985, **32**, 883.
41. M. Phull and P. C. Nigam, *Talanta*, 1981, **28**, 591.
42. H. Lineweaver and D. Burk, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 568.